

20), 3,4-diethoxyphenyl (17–23) and cinnamyl (18–21). The most active among 2-aryl-3-(2',4'-dibutylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-yl)-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinones are bearing (alongwith the zone of inhibition in mm), R=phenyl (17–23), anisyl (17–24), *p*-hydroxyphenyl (19–22), *m*-hydroxyphenyl (17–22), salicyl (17–22), 3,4-dimethoxyphenyl (18–22), *p*-chlorophenyl (19–20) and *o*-chlorophenyl (17–18). In case of 2-aryl-3-(2',4'-dibutylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-yl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones, maximum activity was shown by those compounds bearing (alongwith the zone of inhibition in mm), R=anisyl (17–24), *p*-hydroxyphenyl (17–22), *m*-hydroxyphenyl (18–20), salicyl (18–19), cinnamyl (18–21), 3,4-dimethoxyphenyl (17–20).

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Studies on Benzimidazole. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-(α -Arylamino-benzyl)benzimidazoles and 2-(2',3'-Diaryl-4'-keto-5'-thiazolidinyl)methylbenzimidazoles

G. C. KAMDAR, D. J. BHATT and A. R. PARIKH*

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University,
Rajkot-360 005

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BENZIMIDAZOLE derivatives possess anti-malarial¹, local anaesthetic², antipyretic³, anti-bacterial⁴, goitrogenic⁵ and antibiotic⁶ activities.

α -Substituted-arylacetic acids possess analgesics⁷, antilipamic⁸ and antiinflammatory⁹ activities. 4-Thiazolidinones are known for their biological activities, like hypnotic¹⁰, anaesthetic¹¹, antifungal¹², etc. The α -arylaminoacetonitriles¹⁴ obtained by the action of different aromatic amines on different aromatic aldehydecyanohydrin were treated with concentrated sulphuric acid for 24 h leading to the formation of amide. The amides were then refluxed with aqueous sodium hydroxide to give α -arylamino-phenylacetic acid¹⁵. The arylaminophenyl acetic acids were condensed with *o*-phenylenediamine to get benzimidazole of type 1. The aromatic amine

like aniline, *p*-iodoaniline, *p*-aminoacetophenone, and *o*-phenetidine were condensed with aromatic aldehydes like benzaldehyde, and hydroxy-, bromo-, chloro- and methoxy-benzaldehyde to get the Schiff bases which were then condensed with thiomalic acid to obtain 2,3-diaryl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone^{13,16}. They were condensed with *o*-phenylenediamine to get benzimidazoles of type 2. The constitution was supported by ir spectra (KBr), $\nu_{\max}$ 3 000, 3 200 (NH), 850 and 890 cm^{-1} (polymeric association) through intermolecular hydrogen bond¹⁷. The products were screened for anti-bacterial activity.

TABLE 1—2-(α -ARYLAMINO-BENZYL)BENZIMIDAZOLES (1)

R	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
Phenyl	Phenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃	158–60	62
Phenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃	151–53	63
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃	184–85	69
Phenyl	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	162	61
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	192–93	68
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ Cl	148–49	61
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Aceto-phenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	128–30	67
<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ ClN ₃	172–73	60
<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ ClN ₃	180–81	61

Antibacterial activity: All benzimidazoles were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by cup-plate method¹⁸ using propylene glycol at a concentration 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of the test solution. 2 (where ; R=phenyl ; and R'=phenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyl, *o*- and *p*-anisyl) showed good activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* (30 mm). In case of compounds of type 2 except R'=phenyl, *o*-ethoxyphenyl, *p*-iodophenyl, *p*-acetophenyl and R=phenyl, 3,5-dibromo-3-hydroxyphenyl, are highly active against *S. aureus* (zone of inhibition 38–44 mm).

TABLE 2—2-[2',3'-DIARYL-4'-KETO-5'-THIAZOLIDINYL]METHYLBENZIMIDAZOLES (2)

R	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
Phenyl	Phenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	125-26	52
Phenyl	<i>o</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	184-85	50
<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Phenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	151-52	53
<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Phenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	181-82	43
<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Phenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	166-68	48
3-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	Phenyl	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	300	52
3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	Phenyl	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	166-68	50
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Phenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	160-61	48
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Phenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	170-71	52
VenilinyI	Phenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	147-48	48
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ IN ₃ O ₂ S	150	64
<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ IN ₃ O ₂ S	238	62
<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ IN ₃ O ₂ S	283	60
<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ IN ₃ O ₂ S	250	66
3-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ BrIN ₃ O ₂ S	222	68
3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	C ₂₃ H ₁₂ Br ₂ IN ₃ O ₂ S	154	70
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ClIN ₃ O ₂ S	209	58
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ClIN ₃ O ₂ S	167	66
<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenyl	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ IN ₃ O ₂ S	276	70
α -Furfuryl	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ IN ₃ O ₂ S	166	48
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Acetophenyl	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	169	60
<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Acetophenyl	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	162	62
<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Acetophenyl	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	171	60
<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Acetophenyl	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	139	64
3-Bromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Acetophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	210	68
3,5-Dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Acetophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	138	70
4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Acetophenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	196	67
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Acetophenyl	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	185	58
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Acetophenyl	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	169	69

The activity is not comparable with the known antibiotics like chloromycetin (50 mm).

Experimental

2-(α -Phenylaminophenyl)benzimidazole: A mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine (0.01 mol), α -phenylaminophenylacetic acid (0.01 mol) and absolute ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 10 h. The mixture was poured into ice-water and the product was filtered and washed with water and sodium bicarbonate solution. The crude product was crystallised from ethanol (Found: C, 79.81; H, 5.52; N, 14.00. C₂₀H₁₇N₃ requires: C, 80.26; H, 5.68; N, 14.04%). Similarly, other α -phenylaminophenylacetic acids were condensed with *o*-phenylenediamines. All product gave correct elemental analysis. The physical constants are recorded in Table 1.

2-(2',3'-Diphenyl-4'-keto-5'-thiazolidinyl)methylbenzimidazoles: A mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine (0.01 mole) and 2,3-diphenyl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones (0.01 mol) was heated at 150-60° for 2 h. The mixture was poured into ice-water. The product was filtered and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and hot water, and crystallised from ethanol (Found: C, 71.7; H, 5.3; N, 10.43. C₂₃H₁₉N₃OS requires: C, 71.82; H, 5.23; N, 10.90%).

Similarly, other 2,3-diaryl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones were condensed with *o*-phenylenediamine. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental

analysis. The physical data are recorded in Table 2.

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